

The legal Aspects of Banking Taxation: an Analysis of the global Regulations

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the complex landscape of international banking taxation and its implications for multinational banks. It analyzes the fundamental principles of international taxation, the diverse approaches adopted by individual countries, and the global efforts aimed at achieving tax harmonization. Beyond examining domestic tax regulations governing banks' business earnings, the research also explores foreign tax regimes affecting income, derivative flows, and dividend payments. A central focus is placed on the OECD's Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS) framework, evaluating how its measures influence and reshape banking taxation practices. The study covers a broad range of related topics, including transfer pricing, shadow banking, global trade, group treasury operations, withholding taxes, green banking, microfinance, and sector-specific bank taxes. The findings highlight significant cross-jurisdictional differences in taxation systems while illustrating the effects of international frameworks and treaties on banking activities. Two case studies, Spain Case 281/2012 and Deutsche Bank AG (C-44/11), are analyzed to demonstrate how tax principles are applied in practice. Moreover, the thesis examines tax avoidance within the banking sector and discusses the relevant clauses of the OECD Model Tax Convention in detail. The content of the dissertation shall guide to problem-solving and understanding international tax challenges originating from banking and mastering international taxation issues arising from banking.

Introduction

Taxation in banking is a wide topic of significant importance and this dissertation is developed through personal research on the subject to provide an understanding of the issues related. The research is based on literature on the topic with specific focus on the book “International Taxation of Banking”, by John Abrahamson (2020). International banking taxation, as analyzed in the dissertation, refers to the set of laws and regulations governing the taxation of banking activities that take place across national borders; with globalization and the growth of the financial industry, multinational banks face significant challenges in navigating the varying tax regimes across different jurisdictions. The thesis is characterized by four different parts: the first chapter analyses banks considering the main activities, associated risks, and relationship with the industry and regulatory framework. The impact of Basel III regulatory capital standards on multinational structures and, in particular, the need for more capital and the associated restrictions on the amount of debt, remains the banking sector’s defining characteristic. The second part focuses on OECD’s Model Tax Treaty and BEPS, with an analysis of the Spain case study 281/2012, which provides an example of the OECD approach. The third chapter focuses on different taxation issues and how they are treated in different jurisdictions, with the examination of the Deutsche Bank AG (C- 44/11) case. The analysis includes looking at domestic tax laws related to bank company profits, as well as international tax issues related to income and derivative flows and the payment of dividends. The fourth and final chapter addresses innovation in banking and discusses specific topics regarding activities, and tax and non-tax incentives made by different jurisdictions. The study also explores the implications of tax evasion and avoidance and its effects on the stability of the global financial system. The research uses a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to draw insights from tax policies and differences among jurisdictions and provide an analysis of different taxation issues. The taxation of international banking activities is a critical issue for governments worldwide. It is important to ensure that banks operating across borders pay their fair share of taxes, while also promoting international trade and investment. The findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities of international banking taxation, enabling policymakers, regulators, and industry stakeholders to make informed decisions that promote a fair and sustainable tax environment.

Chapter I: Regulatory Frameworks in Banking

Characteristics of the banking industry

The banking industry provides both significant benefits and risks to national economies, meaning it is fundamental to address any potential issues with bank regulatory frameworks. The current regulatory capital framework has been agreed upon between the central banks as part of the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, and it aims to limit bank debt while simultaneously guaranteeing liquidity against any potential losses and deposit withdrawals. These Bank regulations are based on the BIS Basel III framework and member country bank regulators: in the European Union the ECB grants sole licensing authority over all member state banks under the Single Supervisory Mechanism (SSM). The ECB, being a central bank, does not only keep price stability and conduct economic and monetary policies, but it must also ensure safety and soundness of the whole European banking system. The banking Industry is always changing and developing, and it is concerned with different issues depending on the activities of the bank. Retail and commercial banks issue bonds and lend money to people and businesses, but their primary interest is collecting money through deposits. To safeguard depositors and the financial system, deposits must be supervised. National authorities are in charge of the overseeing, for instance in the United Kingdom the regulatory framework is composed of three organizations, the Bank of England's Prudential Regulations Authority (PRA), providing day-to-day regulations, the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), which ensures that markets operate effectively, and the Bank of England's Financial Policy Committee (FPC) which monitors and takes action to remove or reduce systematic risks to the stability of the country. Several nations additionally offer depositor protection up to predetermined thresholds for certain deposits, in the UK's example GBP 85,000. There are several principal forms of deposits: Current accounts allow customers deposit funds that they can withdraw on demand, Savings accounts reward depositors with interest, Money Market Accounts pay interest based on the current market rate, Call Deposit Accounts allow customers to access deposits including cheque facilities, while also paying interest, and lastly, Term Deposits, which require funds in the account and provide higher interest rates. Loan supply is another essential function of commercial banking; compared to other types of financing, lending has reduced transaction costs for the borrower, and the interest rate charged is influenced by several variables, including the terms of the loan, the risk involved, the loan covenants, market risks, and the presence of high-risk assets. These loans can be syndicated, meaning several banks, rather than just one, are funding them. When the terms and conditions of the loan agreed between lender and borrower are clearly defined, the loans are known as Committed facilities which typically have durations of 2 to 7 years and can be structured as term loans, revolving loans, or syndicated

loans. Uncommitted facilities, which are contracts without a commitment to provide a certain sum of money, are typically used for paying taxes, paying salaries, and making minor purchases. The regulatory environment and taxation challenges are quite different for investment banks, which underwrite the issue of new shares or bonds, are involved in Sales and Trading and Asset management, and aid companies in mergers and acquisitions where they conduct due diligence to target companies. First listed shares, IPOs, are purchased by the bank for sale to investors, and the risk for the bank is that the securities cannot be on-sold. The related listing requirements are established by the stock exchange regulator in that country. The location of the offering is also significant for tax issues such as tax rates on income, capital structure, and tax treaty networks to reduce foreign withholding taxes. Investment banks also assist with underwriting capital by issuing bonds and publicly traded debt; the issues are related to the credit risk of the issuer and the likelihood of default. In these transactions, investment banks receive an underwriting spread, known as gross spread or discount, which equals the amount received from selling the securities less the amount previously paid to obtain them. The bank bears the risk of potential losses on sales and of overestimation of demand for the underwritten issue. The Directive (EU) 2019/2034 (IFD) and the Regulation (EU) 2019/2033, which make up the new prudential framework, were developed by the European Commission in response to the variety and distinct risk profiles of these entities that were not always sufficiently reflected by the banking prudential framework (IFR). By retaining systemic investment enterprises under the prudential standards and oversight of the Capital Requirements Regulation and Capital Requirements Directive (CRR/CRD), the new framework strives to create an adequate and proportional framework for investment firms. This new framework intends to guarantee the secure operation of investment businesses, bolster their soundness and stability, and improve the way they manage risks posed by clients, the market, and the firms themselves.

Bank profitability and risk

The banking industry is characterized by high leverages, since borrowing funds, rather than equity, is used for funding assets such as loans expected to profit, meaning that potential risks also increase. Bank profitability and risk are closely interconnected, and banks must carefully manage their risks to maintain sustainable profitability over the long term. The profitability of a bank can be affected by different factors:

- Asset structure and quality: profitability increases when riskier loans are preferred to more secure assets and poor credit quality has negative effects on bank profitability, while high credit quality increases it.
- Interest rates and Capitalization: increasing interest rates usually benefit bank profitability, and better-capitalized banks can profit by lowering interest expenses on uninsured debt.

- Economic growth and Inflation: a strong economy benefits banks since it increases demand for credit by businesses and households and improves the solvency of borrowers; banks are also affected by inflation which can increase bank salaries and operating costs.
- Revenue diversification: new types of income can contribute to bank profitability.
- Size and Industry concentration: larger banks have more opportunities and can benefit from economies of scale and a more concentrated sector may provide more market power. All these factors may lead a bank to undergo riskier activities to be more profitable, the risks related to these activities are:

(A) Credit risk

It is based on the potential that a borrower or counterparty fails to meet obligations in the agreed terms and loans are the largest source of this type of risk. Banks manage credit risk through a range of methods, including credit analysis, credit policies, credit monitoring, loan portfolio management, and collateralization.

(B) Market risk

Banks may also possess portfolios of traded instruments (bonds, shares, currencies) for short-term profitability. Market risks include risks associated with changes in interest rates, exchange rates, commodity prices, and other market variables that can impact a bank's financial performance.

(C) Liquidity risk

It is the risk of a bank not being capable of funding increases in assets and meeting its obligations as they come due, without affecting its daily operations and incurring unacceptable losses. The liquidity Coverage Ratio is the main tool used to monitor the risk, and measures require banks to hold sufficient liquid assets to withstand a 30-day funding scenario.

(D) Operational risk

Risk of loss resulting from inadequacies in internal processes, systems, human error, or external events. Effective management of operational risk is critical to the success of a bank, as it can impact the bank's reputation, financial performance, and ability to meet regulatory requirements.

Basel III Framework

In response to the Global financial crises, this framework was developed to offset all risks related to banking. The post-crisis regulatory reforms were endorsed by the Group of Central Bank Governors and Heads of Supervision (GHOS), the Basel Committee's oversight body, on 7 December 2017. Adjustments to the market risk framework were endorsed by the GHOS on 14 January 2019. The revised standards aimed to make banks more resilient and restore confidence in banking systems. Basel III's first pillar, which addresses capital requirements, makes a distinction between Tier 1 Capital, which banks may use to cover losses without stopping trade,

and Tier 2 Capital, which only absorbs losses in winding-up situations. Capital requirements are expressed as capital percentage required to be held against a bank’s risk-weighted assets (RWA), Basel III includes a minimum common equity of 4.5% of RWA, with minimum total Tier 1 and Tier 2 capital of 8% of RWA and a capital conservation buffer of 2.5% of risk-weighted assets. This means that common equity plus conservation buffer is 7% while the Minimum Capital (Tier 1 and 2) is 10.5%.

	Common equity	Tier 1 Capital	Total Capital
<i>New minimum ratios</i>	4.5%	6.0%	8%
<i>Conservation buffer</i>	2.5%		
<i>New minimum ratio plus conservation buffer</i>	7.0%	8.5%	10.5%

Table 1: Basel III Capital ratio requirements as a percentage of risk-weighted assets.

Following the second pillar of the framework, off-balance sheet exposures, securitization operations, valuation procedures, and interest rate risks associated with the management process are all included. The promotion of regulatory disclosure obligations, including credit, operational, and leverage risks, is covered in further detail in Pillar 3. For systemically significant institutions, which are determined employing quantitative and qualitative factors including size, activity, complexity, and interconnection, Basel III additionally stipulates extra criteria for capital pillars. Basel III also establishes new liquidity requirements that banks must meet to ensure they have sufficient funding to meet their obligations during times of financial stress. Banks are required to maintain a net stable funding ratio (NSFR) of at least 100% to ensure they have a stable funding base, and a liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) of at least 100% to ensure they have sufficient high-quality liquid assets to cover their short-term funding needs. The framework introduces new standards for measuring and managing counterparty credit risk in derivatives and other financial transactions, and a leverage ratio requirement that banks must meet to ensure they have adequate capital to support their activities. Banks are required to maintain a leverage ratio of at least 3% of their total exposures in order to mitigate risks, and this is particularly important to avoid bank crisis.

Chapter II: International Taxation

Tax Treaties and BEPS

Different tax issues may arise from banking activities, primarily from double taxation and international income concerning the payment of dividends out of the profits of a local country company to the foreign parent company, and any possible withholding tax on the dividends. Generally, dividends are not deductible expenses, but they may be tax-free to the parent company shareholders and exemptions may arise under certain rules such as the European Union Subsidiary Directive. In addition to the credit for international withholding tax, the parent company's connected country may also permit a foreign tax credit known as an underlying foreign tax credit. Although there are various tax implications when it comes to interest payments on loans or corporate bonds, it is usual to maximize local country interest deductions on loans from the parent business or to lower taxable earnings. Many nations, including Germany, Italy, Denmark, and the United States, have restrictions on deductions due to the implementation of interest barrier rules. One form of restriction is thin capitalization, which can prevent deductions on a portion of the debt that is deemed excessive, typically because the company has little share capital compared to related party debt. Germany introduced these rules in 2008 that can disallow interest deductions where the company's net interest expenditure exceeds 30% of the company's EBITDA. Interest, dividends, and royalties payments made to foreign nations are frequently subject to withholding taxes, which are subtracted from the payments as the recipient's tax responsibility and sent to the local tax office. With effect from 2009, the European Union dropped the threshold to 10% and mandated that no withholding tax be applied to dividend payments made between taxable corporations in member nations. Several of these concerns are the subject of tax treaties, which are used to assign rights across nations, eliminate double taxation, and provide a framework for local tax authorities. The following are some of the articles and clauses from the OECD's Model Tax Treaty that are particularly pertinent to the taxation of banking businesses:

Article 5 Permanent Establishments (PE)

They are defined as being "a fixed place of business through which the business of an enterprise is wholly or partially carried on." Thus, there must be a place of business which is fixed and where the enterprise carries on activities. Examples include a workshop, an office, a branch, a factory, and a place of management. The use of facilities to store, display, deliver or collect information does not count as PE, while the use of a dependent agent which habitually concludes contracts on behalf of the enterprise does constitute a form of permanent establishment.

Article 7 Business Profits

The article concerns the division of profits between a PE and its head office and states that the

profits of a PE are the profits it might expect to make if it were a separate and independent entity engaged in similar activities, and these profits may be taxed in other states but only so much of them as is attributable to that permanent establishment.

Article 10 Dividends

This article allocates unlimited taxing rights to the country of residence of the shareholder that receives the dividends. The contracting state of the foreign company who pays the dividends may also tax, but the tax charged shall not exceed 5% when there is significant ownership or 15% in all other cases.

Article 11 Interest

The article assigns taxing rights to interest to the country of residence of the lender, but it allows the source country to also tax the interest if the beneficial owner is a resident in the other contracting state. The tax charged on the gross amount of interest paid to the non-residential beneficiary shall not exceed 10%.

Article 12 Royalties

Article 12 provides that royalties shall be taxed in the country of residence of the beneficial owner, excluding royalties connected to a permanent establishment, in that case they should be subject to article 7 concerning business profits. The definition of royalty is “payments of any kind received as a consideration of the use of, or the right of use, any copyright of literary, artistic or scientific work, including cinematographic films, any patent, trademark, design or model, plan, secret formula or process, or for information concerning the industrial, commercial or scientific experience.”

Chapter V – Elimination of Double Taxation

The OECD allows two ways of eliminating double taxation: Exemption method (Article 23A) requires the residence country to exempt an income from another source country from being taxed, while the Credit Method (Article 23B) recognizes the possibility for the residence country to tax income while allowing a credit for the source country withholding tax. The focus of the OECD also shifted to tax avoidance, and in 2013 they released the Action Plan on Base Erosion and Profit Shifting (BEPS), which includes different measures and actions., necessary to successfully remove double non-taxation and instances of no or low taxation associated with practices that artificially segregate taxable money from the activities that generate it. The developed Action plan is divided in the following steps: Action 1 addresses Tax Challenges of the digital economy; Action 2 is concerned with neutralizing the effects of Hybrid Mismatch Arrangements, while Action 3 aims to strengthen CFC rules. Action 4 is about limiting Base Erosion via interest deductions and other financial payments and Action 5 is to counter harmful Tax Practices more effectively, considering transparency and substance. The objectives of Action 6 and 7 are to prevent Treaty Abuse and the Artificial Avoidance of PE status. Ac-

tions 8,9,10 are all interested in assuring that Transfer Pricing outcomes are in line with value creation. Action 11 establishes methodologies to collect and analyze data on BEPS and the Actions to address it. Action 12 requires taxpayers to disclose their aggressive Tax Planning Arrangements, and Action 13 re-examines Transfer Pricing documentation. Finally, Action 14 aims to make dispute Resolution Mechanisms more effective and Action 15 is concerned with developing a multilateral instrument. Without more openness, transparency, and predictability from companies and institutions, the measures taken to combat BEPS will fail, meaning that fast, precise, and thorough information must be made available in order to help governments swiftly identify danger regions. Several steps may be implemented to rectify the flaws effectively and efficiently in the present guidelines.

Bank Branches, Parent Companies and Representative Offices

The initial stages of developing banking operations in a new country involve important costs in licensing, marketing, and registration; tax issues are whether these initial foreign losses can be deductible in the head office country. There are different ways of taxation treatment depending on the country, the following are two examples:

(A) The United Kingdom

In 2009 the UK adopted an elective regime for exemptions of foreign branch income (profits or losses). The election is irrevocable and can be done on a company-by-company basis, meaning companies in the same group can elect from themselves and have the opportunity to recognize foreign branch losses if the exemption is not made.

(B) Italy

Companies which are residents are subject to corporate income tax worldwide, but there is an elective branch regime from 2016 that provides tax exemption for income generated through permanent establishments while controlling provisions applied to branches located in low-tax countries. The election is irrevocable and applies to all PEs of the bank or company. Other issues may arise from whether dividends received from foreign subsidiaries are free of tax in the parent country, such as under participation exemption provisions. In Italy dividends derived by resident companies from non-residents might be 95% exempt from corporate income, but the exemption does not apply where dividends are deductible to the paying company. A correlated issue is also whether interest deductions are available on borrowings used for funding foreign subsidiaries and branches; related dividend income in many countries can be tax-free, and so tax provisions may deny interest deductions on the related borrowings. While considering the potential tax issues, it is important to analyze the potential benefits of conducting business in foreign branches, such as:

- Efficient use of capital
- Foreign-owned bank branches can take advantage of the parent company's balance sheet and rely on its substantial capital and resources.
- Business Capacity
- Enhanced ability to undertake and participate in more transactions with larger exposures.
- Better integration with global operations.
- Governance
- The branch is directly controlled by the senior management of the parent bank, whereas subsidiaries have a personal board that is responsible for decisions.
- Reduced administrative, and compliance costs and lowered costs of funding. Compliance with the OECD model is fundamental, since some issues may arise concerning business profits (Article 7), exemption of foreign branch profits or tax credit in the head office country (Article 23), or any dividends, interest, and royalty provisions in Articles 10-12 of the Model Tax Treaty. Banks may also prefer to establish a representative office in a foreign country, to perform very limited functions. This can provide increased interaction with customers, government authorities, and industry associations. The representative office shall not be engaged in banking activities, but only in representational and liaison activities such as conducting research and undertaking credit assessments and reports. Issues may arise if these activities exceed the limits and the company engages in forms of banking business such as soliciting and receiving deposits, granting loans, or issuing securities. Article 4 of the OECD model grants representative offices exemption from giving rise to a PE if the activity is purely auxiliary and preparatory. Each individual case must be then analyzed.

Case study on branches: Spain case 281/2012

This case is analyzed as to provide context of certain instances where authorized OECD approach cannot be used to determine profits and free capital attributed to permanent establishments. In this situation, The Spanish National High Court attributed free capital to the Spanish branch of a Netherlands bank, based on solvency ratio requirements in Spain which would have applied to a Spanish bank, therefore disallowing part of the interest deductions claimed by the branch. The fact that a branch of a foreign bank was treated as if it were a domestic bank is fundamental to understand the OECD framework. The related Spain- Netherlands Tax Treaty (1971) did not include the later authorized OECD approach, and the court adopted a static interpretation of the treaty, rejecting a dynamic interpretation calculating the amount of free capital. Such dynamism would constitute an infringement of the principles of non-retroactivity of the Law, legitimate expectations, and good faith.

Chapter III: Taxation issues and Transfer Pricing

Derivatives, loan provisions and debt restructuring

The chapter aims to provide information about tax issues that may arise related to specific topics in banking activities, starting from derivatives. Derivatives are a form of security whose prices derive from one or more underlying assets, which can be shares, bonds, commodities, currencies, market indexes, and interest rates. They constitute a contract between related parties whose value is subject to fluctuations in the price of the underlying assets. The global financial crisis included the risks of these structured financial products and securitization such as collateralized debt obligations (CDO), which are investment products created by pooling many loans, and credit default swaps (CDS), which are derivatives with value based on the risk of default of assets. Tax treatment for derivatives varies between countries, but the International Financial Reporting Standard IFRS 9 requires derivatives to be measured at fair value with changes recognized in the profit or loss. In the Netherlands for example there is no specific tax provision but the Netherlands GAAP accounting and the IFRS 9 are usually followed. There is no withholding tax on derivative payments and interest to non-residents, but there is a withholding tax on dividends which may be reduced or eliminated under specific tax treaties although most swap transactions do not provide dividends. The most common types of derivatives are Options, forward contracts, and swaps.

[A] Swaps

They are agreements to exchange one flow of income for another, most frequently used to hedge interest rate or foreign currency risk. They are usually made on a notional principal contracts basis, while a credit default swap (CDS) is essentially the sale of insurance that provides for a payment by the protection seller in case of specific company defaults. The protection buyer makes periodic payments for this insurance.

[B] Options

Options are financial instruments that provide the right to purchase or sell assets at a later date; the exercise of the option takes place when the option is used to purchase or sell the asset, which will generate a taxable transaction, recognized by banks as unrealized gains and losses based on changes in value based on IFRS 9.

[C] Forwards and Futures

Forward contracts are agreements to purchase or sell assets at specific later dates, differently from options, there is no choice as to whether to buy the asset. A future is just a forward contract in a standardized form that can be traded on a securities exchange. The related tax issues include whether the gain or loss on revenue of capital account, source of the gain, or if withholding taxes apply. Another important tax issue for banking is related to loan provisions

and debt restructuring, by banks where, due to the credit of the borrower, there is concern that the entity may not receive the loan payments and accrued interest. In IFRS 9 impairment of financial assets is based on the Expected Credit Loss (ECL), which is a process based on different stages: firstly, as soon as the financial instrument is originated there is a 12-month expected credit loss allowance, secondly if the credit risk increases then full time expected credit losses are recognized in profit or loss, and lastly, if the risks associated are considered credit-impaired (too high), interest revenue is calculated based on amortized cost, and lifetime expected losses are recognized. Each country has its own approach to loan loss deduction, the write-off method is used in the United States and Korea, where loans are tax-deductible only when declared uncollectible and are written off the bank's books. Almost all other economies use the specific provisions approach, where specific provisions are fully or partially tax deductible. Debt restructuring is used when a company has excessive debt to banking institutions and needs some form of debt relief to continue business and not be liquidated. In a debt restructuring a company's outstanding loan may be waived, meaning the loan balance is reduced. This benefit may be taxed and since it is a loss to the creditor, it may also be deductible for tax purposes. The debt of a company may also be converted into equity using the Debt/Equity approach, where new shares are issued by the borrower, and the loan balance is reduced. If the new shares are worth less than the loan, the benefit is taxed for the debtor and related loss is deductible for the creditor. These approaches vary from country, in the Netherlands for example loan waivers have matching tax treatment, where parties are unrelated, an arm's length waiver is taxable for the debtor and deductible for the creditor. For related parties, a non-arm length waiver by a shareholder is usually treated as a capital contribution, not taxable for the debtor, and not deductible for the creditor. The conversion of debt to equity has matching tax treatment and is made at debt par value which has no tax effect for the debtor. The creditor obtains a deduction for the loss where the fair value of shares is less than the fair value of debt. Any subsequent gain on shares is taxable under the anti-abuse measures.

Value-Added Tax and Financial Transaction taxes

Financial services are usually exempt from Value Added Tax (VAT), known as exempt suppliers, meaning the tax is not chargeable on related income, such as income from foreign exchange transactions or interest income. However, the bank is not entitled to a refund of tax paid, known as input tax, on its purchases; this can lead to a form of hidden charge on financial services, where states have collected tax revenues on inputs related to products and services which are not refunded. On this basis, zero-rated suppliers are better for the supplier company than exempt suppliers, because the former allows the company to receive input tax credits. The European Council's VAT directive requires European Union member states to adopt provisions

that exempt domestic suppliers of specific financial services including insurance and reinsurance transactions, granting and negotiation of credit, and transactions concerning currency, bank notes, deposits, shares, and other securities. For exports of these services, a zero rate may be applied to allow input tax recovery, but the tax treatment is left to the discretion of the member states. Some financial services such as investment, finance, and taxation advice may be partially exempt from VAT, deducting only the amount of input tax related to taxable supplies. There are instances where VAT allows for Value Added Tax grouping, where entities closely linked financially, economically, and organizationally may be regarded as single taxable persons. There may be also provisions for related bad debt relief, allowing claims to recover tax paid where the company's customers are not able to pay their invoices and the use of central billing agencies by multinational groups with companies in several European Union countries. In the latter case, the agency would receive the invoices from all service providers and since they can be accounted as intra-European Union services it may be possible to recover tax in the same return using a reverse charge mechanism. There are other taxes imposed on banking activities such as financial transaction taxes (FTT) which are imposed on transactions such as the sale and purchase of financial instruments such as stocks, shares, or foreign exchange transactions. They include several long-standing taxes such as stamp duties, securities transaction taxes, capital levies, bank transaction taxes and, currency transaction taxes. FTT in Italy can apply to Shares with an average market capitalization greater than EUR 500m, or with derivatives, if more than 50% of their underlying reference value relates to in-scope Italian shares, and with High-Frequency Trades generated by computer systems where the ratio of orders amended or cancelled in a time frame shorter than half a second exceeds 60% of total entered. The rate of tax is 0.02% on high-frequency trades, 0.1% on exchanged traded equities, and 0.2% on over-the-counter equities. While FTT constitutes great importance, bank levies and financial stability contributions are the most common form of additional tax imposed on banks, which are different depending on the country. France for example has a Systematic Risk Tax that applies to the minimum amount of own funds required to comply with the coverage ratio, in 2018 at 0.141%. Austria has a bank levy that applies to total liabilities net of equity and insured deposits, at 0.024% from EUR 300m to EUR 20b, and 0.029% over EUR 20b with a surcharge of 45% on the tax amount.

Deutsche Bank AG (C-44/11)

This is a case concerning financial service exemption between Deutsche Bank and the German Bundesfinanzhof (Federal Finance Court). The case is related to the taxpayer using its own advice concerning purchases and sales of securities, and then executing the decisions as an intermediary on behalf of clients. Deutsche Bank offered portfolio management services to investors

either directly or through its subsidiaries. The bank was given instructions by investors to manage their securities based on predetermined investment strategies, which included acquiring and disposing of securities on their behalf. The bank provided two services: analyzing and monitoring the assets of the investors and buying and selling securities. In return for these services, it charged an annual fee of 1.8% of the value of the assets managed. This fee included a 1.2% fee for asset management and a 0.6% fee for buying and selling securities. Despite reporting its income as VAT exempt in its German VAT returns, German authorities disagreed and argued that the services provided by the bank were taxable. The ECJ decided that two components make up a securities-based asset management service, like the one at issue in the main proceedings, and they are objectively considered to be one economic supply. It must be understood that securities-based asset management, such as that at issue in the main proceedings, is not exempt from value-added tax under Article 135(1)(f) or (g) of Council Directive 2006/112/EC of November 28 2006, on the Common System of Value-Added Tax, meaning taxpayer's service shall not count as financial advice or financial intermediary service, but as a single supply of a third kind which is not qualified to be exempt.

Intangible Property and Tax avoidance

Intangible property (IP) refers to an item of value that cannot be touched or physically held, and since it is a crucial component of banking operations, it may cause tax concerns. When taking into account IP in mergers and acquisitions, businesses pay royalties or management fees for the use of the intangible property as a deduction under several tax regimes. Additionally, there are several tax breaks for research and development (RD), allowing a tax credit for costs that would otherwise be capitalized. Patent box regimes, which have been adopted by various nations like Belgium, France, Portugal, and the United Kingdom, are the most important trend in tax breaks. These measures are usually counted as output tax incentives since they relate to income deriving from the activity, for example providing a lower taxation regime for royalty income derived from licensing of technology. They differ from input tax incentives which relate to tax deductions, tax credits, and accelerated depreciation on the inputs. Controlled Foreign Companies (CFC) provisions are concerned with addressing tax avoidance structures that use tax havens. While they may not apply to active business revenue derived from production, manufacturing, or trade operations carried out in that country, most laws apply to passive income relating to a foreign corporation based in tax havens or low-rate jurisdictions. Two related tests may be used by the provisions to determine whether a company is a controlled foreign company: a shareholder test is used to determine whether a company is a controlled foreign company because their residents have sufficient control of the foreign company, and a test to check whether taxpayers in their country have sufficient ownership or control in the foreign company. The

United Kingdom provisions require 50% control by one or more United Kingdom residents for a foreign company and then apply the provisions to United Kingdom residents who hold at least 25% shareholding in that foreign company. Anti-tax haven provisions are also included in the terms of the participation exemption. For instance, most European nations have participation exemptions that, under certain conditions, allow profits from other nations to be tax-free or subject to a reduced rate of taxation. This holds when the shareholder receives dividends from a corporation in which they hold a sizeable stake, but they are rejected when the dividend pertains to passive operations carried out by a subsidiary in a low-tax nation. Controlled foreign corporations and related tax evasion were the focus of Action 3 of the OECD BEPS Actions Plan, and the European Union also approved Directive (EU) 2012/1164 (ATAD1), which establishes regulations against tax avoidance practices that impair the operation of the internal market.

Transfer Pricing

Transfer pricing in banking refers to the process of setting prices for transactions between different departments or subsidiaries of a bank located in different countries. These transactions can include the transfer of funds, goods, or services between these entities. In banking, transfer pricing is used to ensure that profits are allocated fairly between different entities of the same bank, using arm's length prices. It also helps banks to optimize their tax liabilities in different jurisdictions where they operate. Transfer pricing can be a complex and sensitive issue, particularly for banks operating across multiple jurisdictions with different tax laws and regulations. Banks are required to comply with transfer pricing regulations and provide documentation to support their pricing decisions. Failure to comply with transfer pricing regulations can result in significant financial penalties and reputational damage. The OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines set out methods for determining arm's length pricing for transactions between related parties: the Comparable uncontrolled price (CUP) method is based on the comparison of prices charged in a controlled transaction to the price charged in an uncontrolled transaction in comparable circumstances. The Resale price method (RPM) is based on the resale price at which a product purchased from a related party would be sold to an independent enterprise. It is calculated by deducting the resale price margin from the resale price in the uncontrolled transaction. The Cost-plus method (CPM) is based on costs incurred by the supplier in a controlled transaction, with a markup added to the costs to determine the arm's length price in the controlled transaction considering the functions performed, risks assumed, and assets employed. A Profit split method is used to identify an appropriate split of the combined profit realized by related entities from a controlled transaction. Lastly, the Transactional net margin method (TNMM) is based on determining the net profit margin from a controlled transaction relative to an appropriate base such as cost, sales, or assets. Taxation issues may arise from the choice of the

tested party, selection of the method and the functional analysis to determine what products or services are provided and with which related and unrelated parties. The main transfer pricing issue for most banks and tax authorities is to determine an arm's length attribution of profits to their foreign branches. The OECD approach recognizes transactions between the head office and the branch for taxation purposes, and it is based on the functions performed, assets used, and risks assumed analysis of the traditional banking business. It also takes into consideration Key Entrepreneurial Risk-Taking functions (KERT) in creating and subsequently managing a loan. The attribution of profits is a two-step process, the first step is a functional and factual analysis, leading to the attribution to the establishment as appropriate of the rights and obligations arising out of the transactions, attribution of capital, identification of KERT, and relevant people functions, and then the recognition and determination of the nature of those dealings between the establishment and other parts of the enterprise. The second step is pricing using an arm's length basis through the determination of comparability between dealings and uncontrolled transactions, and the selection and application of the most appropriate method to the circumstances of the case and the guidelines. Branch profits are a significant taxation issue also for global trading structures, that execute customers' orders in financial markets around the world at all times and require adequate capitalization, creditworthiness, technology, and risk-taking strategies. There are instances when a parent company or treasury company may make a loan to another company in the group to fund a new business, or finance business expansion, meaning it requires an arm's length interest rate of the loan that should be equal to an interest rate charged between unrelated parties in similar facts and circumstances. The OECD BEPS action plan also includes a special review of transfer pricing relating to intra-group funding as part of Action 9, to ensure that transfer pricing outcomes are in line with value creation/risks and capital. There is an issue of whether the amount of interest on such loans should be grossed up for local country withholding tax using the arm's length principle since a third-party lender would generally require such grossing up. However, the local subsidiary may be able to obtain a loan from a local bank without the need to gross up for the tax; there is no common practice in these instances, but the related point is that a foreign lending company may potentially be able to obtain a foreign tax credit for withholding tax. The transfer or provision of intangible property to related parties should also be made based on an arm's length consideration. Intangible property plays an important role in the banking industry because it enables banks to differentiate themselves from their competitors and generate revenue from their unique offerings. For example, a bank may have a proprietary software system that allows it to offer more efficient services to customers. Alternatively, a bank may have a trademarked brand that is recognized and valued by customers. The OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines 2017 require that all members of a group receive appropriate compensation for the functions they perform, assets they use, and

risks they assume. This analysis is made through the determination of which members perform and exercise control over development, enhancement, maintenance, protection, and exploitation functions (DEMPE). Transfer pricing in service transactions can be made through Allocation keys, used to allocate costs or revenues to different departments or products within an organization. They are typically based on certain criteria or factors, such as sales revenue, number of employees, or square footage of space used. In the context of transfer pricing, allocation keys can be used to allocate the profits or costs associated with a transaction between related parties. For example, if a company's sales are split equally between two divisions, then the profits from a related-party transaction should also be split equally between those two divisions. Using allocation keys can help ensure that transfer pricing is conducted fairly and equitably, and that profits and costs are allocated in a manner that accurately reflects the contributions of each department or division.

Chapter IV: Innovations and developments in banking

Banking for society: Green Banking and Microfinance Banking

Green and microfinance banking are both aimed at contributing to the welfare of society and create a benefit using different approaches. Green finance integrates environmental and social considerations into all aspects of banking operations, including lending, investment, risk management, and internal operations. It aims to promote sustainable development and reduce the environmental impact of banking activities, while also promoting social and economic development. It includes a range of practices, such as financing renewable energy projects, promoting energy efficiency, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and supporting sustainable agriculture and forestry. In addition to promoting sustainable development, green banking can also offer benefits for banks themselves. It can help reduce operational costs by promoting energy efficiency and resource conservation and can also enhance the reputation of banks by demonstrating a commitment to environmental and social responsibility. There are different examples of green projects in banking, such as the KfW Renewable Energies Programme in Germany, which was developed to support initiatives related to the environment plants for electricity generation from renewable energy sources with a long-term, interest-reduced loan with repayment bonuses. Tax incentives are an important tool that governments can use to encourage green finance, which refers to financial activities that support environmentally sustainable projects and businesses. Incentives can take various forms, including tax credits, deductions, exemptions, and preferential tax rates, and are designed to provide financial benefits to businesses and individuals who invest in or support green finance activities. Examples include Chile, where foreign institutional investors are exempt from tax on bonds related to green finance, and Brazil which allows a

full exemption for investments in bonds with proceeds for infrastructure including construction and wind energy. Microfinance on the other hand, is a financial service that provides small loans and other financial products to low-income individuals and households, who often lack access to traditional banking services. Microfinance is intended to promote financial inclusion, entrepreneurship, and poverty reduction by enabling low-income individuals to start or expand small businesses, invest in education or health, and build financial assets. Microfinance is typically provided by microfinance institutions (MFIs), which are specialized financial institutions that serve low-income clients. MFIs typically offer small loans, savings accounts, insurance, and other financial services, often in combination with training and other non-financial services to support clients' business and financial management skills. Tax incentives can encourage investment in microfinance institutions and microfinance projects, thereby increasing the availability of financial services to low-income clients and promoting financial inclusion. Some examples of tax incentives for microfinance include Tax credits for investments in MFIs, meaning governments can offer tax credits to individuals or institutions, providing a financial incentive to support microfinance activities and Tax exemptions or reduced taxes for MFIs, decreasing their operating costs and allowing them to provide financial services at lower costs to their clients. Governments can also allow individuals or corporations to deduct donations to microfinance projects from their taxable income, providing an incentive for philanthropic support of microfinance activities. There are also instances of non-tax incentives which can include government funding subsidies and bond guarantees.

Non-traditional financial intermediation: Fintech and Shadow Banking

Fintech is a term that refers to the application of technology to financial services intending to improve the efficiency, accessibility, and affordability of financial products and services. Fintech encompasses a broad range of financial activities, including payments, lending, investing, insurance, and wealth management, and includes a variety of technological innovations, such as mobile apps, digital platforms, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and machine learning. Fintech has emerged as a rapidly growing industry in recent years, driven by advances in technology, changes in consumer behavior, and regulatory reforms. It has the potential to disrupt traditional financial services by providing faster, more convenient, and more customized financial products and services to consumers and businesses. Several countries provide non-tax incentives, such as the regulatory framework for crowdfunding activities introduced in France in 2014, which was intended to develop crowdfunding while also providing investor protection and information. This included exemption from public offering rules such as prospectus requirements. Incentives in the United Kingdom include the Innovation Hub and the Regulatory Sandbox to support innovation in the interests of consumers established by the Financial Conduct Authority. Other

countries such as Australia decided to adopt tax incentives to support fintech, which include exemption from tax on share profits made on eligible investments, flow-through tax treatment and a non-refundable carry forward tax up to 10% for limited partners. Shadow banking refers to a system of financial intermediation that operates outside the traditional banking sector, involving non-bank financial institutions that provide credit, liquidity, and other financial services to borrowers. The term "shadow" refers to the fact that these financial activities take place outside the formal banking sector and are therefore less regulated and less transparent, which include financial instruments like credit default swaps. Shadow banking activities include a variety of financial transactions, such as securities lending, repurchase agreements (repos), asset-backed commercial paper, and money market funds. These activities are typically conducted by investment banks, hedge funds, insurance companies, and other non-bank financial institutions that operate similarly to banks but are not subject to the same regulatory oversight. The European Commission noted the importance of regulating this sector since it constitutes around 30% of the total financial system. Shadow banking presents several tax issues, mainly related to its complex and often opaque structure, including tax evasion and avoidance, transfer pricing, tax arbitrage, and lack of transparency.

Automatic exchange of information

The automatic exchange of information (AEOI) is a system designed to facilitate the sharing of financial information between countries, intending to prevent tax evasion and improve tax compliance. AEOI requires financial institutions, such as banks, to collect information about their customers' financial accounts, including balances, interest income, and capital gains, and report this information to the tax authorities in their own country. The tax authorities then share this information with their counterparts in other countries, under the framework of bilateral or multilateral agreements. AEOI is typically implemented using Common Reporting Standards (CRS), which provide a standardized format for reporting financial information. CRS was developed by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and endorsed by the G20 in 2014. Currently, over 100 countries have committed to implementing CRS. An example of regulation is FATCA, which stands for the Foreign Account Tax Compliance Act. It is a US law that was enacted in 2010 to combat tax evasion by US taxpayers who hold foreign financial accounts, and it requires foreign financial institutions (FFIs) to report information about financial accounts held by US taxpayers to the US Internal Revenue Service (IRS). FFIs that fail to comply with FATCA reporting requirements may face penalties and sanctions, including being subject to a 30% withholding tax on certain payments made to them by US sources. FATCA has also inspired other countries to implement similar reporting requirements, including the OECD's Common Reporting Standards (CRS).

Conclusion

This thesis has introduced and discussed significant topics concerning the international taxation of banking. The most significant finding is the high rate of change and evolution of the regulatory environment and corresponding tax regulations. With the OECD issuing guidance on the linked transfer pricing difficulties and the focus on the related crucial entrepreneurial risk-taking functions, the regulatory Basel III framework, also gives birth to the broad usage of bank branches. The most significant international tax development has been the extension of transfer pricing provisions to enforce those provisions. The need to address this issue of tax risk management has been recognised by multinational groups with the increased use of Advance Pricing Agreements to obtain agreement on arm's length pricing. The usage of bilateral and multilateral agreements, when the tax authorities in two or more countries approve the transfer pricing utilised by a multinational business, has expanded in recent years. An important development is the growing application of general anti-avoidance regulations, which may potentially result in a decrease in the adoption of more aggressive tax structures. The landscape of taxation has been drastically changed by Base Erosion and Profit Shifting policies. Action 3 on CFC measures, Action 4 on interest deductions, Action 6 on treaty abuse, Action 7 on preventing the artificial avoidance of permanent establishment status, and Actions 8–10 on transfer pricing, including global value chains and intangible property, were among the numerous developments addressed by the measures. Controlled foreign company measures and associated disclosure requirements for tax haven transactions are increasingly addressing the use of tax havens and low tax regimes to derive income such as dividends, interest, and royalties. The Base Erosion and Profit Shifting measures, particularly the Country-by-Country reporting requirements in Action 13 and their implementation in the OECD 2017 Transfer Pricing Guidelines, contain safeguards against the use of tax havens. Additionally, there is a focus on enhancing global reporting and collaboration, employing agreements with low-tax nations structures that include provisions for information exchange. There have been improvements that could be advantageous to multinational corporations, such as the elimination of double taxation under Action 12's Mutual Agreement Procedure and Action 15's related treaty shopping prevention measures in the Multilateral Instrument. Whether the specified measures will be included into the relevant nations' tax laws and treaties, including the acceptance of the Multilateral Instrument, is the most important connected issue. The 2017 OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines have expanded the scope of transfer pricing analysis by treating business restructurings based on profit potential, analysing the development, enhancement, maintenance, protection, and exploitation of intangibles, and treating intangibles that are difficult to value. Whether the current OECD focus on the digital economy might encompass associated financial services like Internet banking is one potential future development. Addressing the increasingly intricate beneficial ownership and

control arrangements under these global reporting regimes is one of the related concerns. The range of international banking activities is expanding, including green banking, where financial institutions raise money for renewable energy projects, microfinance, where people with very low incomes can access banking services, and shadow banking, where financial services are offered outside of the framework for banking regulation, supervision, and risk management. With the present review of the reliance on regulatory capital constraints to limit gearing and related interest deductions, the policy framework for the taxes of banking is also shifting. The framework addresses the implementation of particular bank taxes and financial transaction taxes, as well as the question of whether they may be better targeted to address transactions that raise financial risks in national and international economies. The significance of tax governance and tax risk management for multinational banking is highlighted by these developments. A lot of new international tax challenges will be presented by the banking industry, which is still one of the most fascinating sectors of international economic activity.

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